

SUBJECTIVE QUESTIONS ANSWERING SYSTEM CONCEPTS, APPROACHES AND TRACKS: A SURVEY

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Abstract:

Question answering System (QAS) represents a specialized information retrieval (IR) mechanism. The QAS is concerned with relevant answers that are given to the proposed questions in natural language. It is increasingly needed in education, and especially it is used as a tool for automated subjective exam assessment. Most QAS is composed of three main components: classification of questions, retrieval of information, and retrieval of an answer. The classification of questions plays an essential role in QASs by categorizing the submitted question according to its type. Retrieval of information is used for answering a question because if a document does not have the correct answers, no further processing can be done to find the answer. Finally, the retrieval of an answer is performed to retrieve the answer to the question the user is asking. This research paper includes an overview of the automat assessment systems for subjective questions in English and other languages, as well as previous related tasks that compare each research against another. In conclusion, the survey provides an analytical discussion of the proposed models in subjective exam assessment and their key contributions, test results, and limitations

Keywords: natural language processing, Automatic Subjective assessment system, online examination, Question Analysis.

1. Introduction

1.1 Online Examination system

An online Examination System is a wide technology. It gets benefits to simplify activities and define many of the questions. The online examination system is more effective; the time is not spent in the evaluation process with easy access, more security depends on authentication, and reduces the number of papers. Candidate's operations appear by using any devices like desktop, laptop with the browser. The examination management tracks and records candidates' answers and statistical analysis of students' grade [1]. In the traditional examination, the invigilators required more time and the processing of results takes a long time because it is done manually [2].

Automatic question answering (AQA) can be written back in the 1960s; however, it is always compatible with specialized expert programs only [3], [4]. Researchers also tried AQA programs based on the closed Corpora, marked on tagged corpora [5], [6], or knowledge bases [7], [8], [9]. The researchers have tried again they build QA programs in large document collections on the Web by combining retrievable information with the most advanced data retrieval technics [10], [11]. The researchers have been attracted by the task of building open-domain QA programs based on the collection of real world records, especially the World Wide Web [12], [13], [14].

Computer-assisted assessment is a term that encompasses all forms of assessment, whether summaries (eg tests that will provide formal instruction) or examinations conducted (e.g. learning tests but not part of course marks), submitted with the help of computers [15]. This includes all computer-assisted tests, whether online or offline, as well as computer-assisted labels, such as those using Optical Mark Reading (OMR). There are several open source online tools for handling tests performed on OMR sheets [16]. Some CAA methods do not require an understanding of the sophisticated text. Also, there are some wildering answers made with free text that you may need text analysis. Higgins et al. [17] developed Online Essay Evaluation Service embeds naming capacities into understudy composing for exposition based oral material and their where depict another framework that improves Criterion's ability, by assessing numerous parts of cognizance in papers. This framework recognizes highlights of sentences dependent on semantic closeness measures and speech structure. A help vector machine utilizes these highlights to catch breakdown confusion because of relatedness to the exposition question and relatedness between talk components. Intra-sentential quality is assessed with rule-based heuristics. Lea-cock and Chodorow [18] design C-rater is an automated scoring engine that has been developed to score responses to content-based short answer questions. It is not simply a string matching program; instead, it uses predicate argument structure, pronominal reference, morphological analysis, and synonyms to assign full or partial credit to a short answer question. C-rater has been used in two studies: National Assessment for Educational Progress (NAEP) and a state-wide assessment in Indiana. In both studies, the c-rater agreed with human graders about 84% of the time.

Pulman and Sukkarieh [19], Mohler and Mihalcea [20] are the basis of this work. Most of the previous automated testing program [21] includes word comparison strategies. Dignified text comparisons have also been discussed with cheeking grammar [22]. This solves the problem of inconsistencies in responses. In the current activity, students' natural way of answering questions is assessed and their points are entered accurately, by comparing teachers or model answers with their answers. The challenge lies in the correct assessment of the various written answers by the learners that have led to the assessment of the subject knowledge acquired by the learners. The program proposes a learning approach by incorporating natural language strategies to identify the extent of responses, thereby providing an answer to deepen the learner's topic understanding.

A significance of the proposed efficient automated assessment system for subjective questions should have the following features: most of the capabilities for automated assessment systems are without the need for human intervention, decreasing in computational complexity to provide a fast-automated assessment for subjective examination, and the efficient capability allow setting exam papers and quizzes in every semester. The main objectives in a subjective examination are to analyze the process of the traditional examination system, to find the gaps for improvement, automate the activity of manual assessment of subjective answers, to present a method based on similarity measures, which provide the user with a value of similarity between the two documents sand to study the percentage of matching of two documents (model answer and student answer) that will display in terms of marks scored. In the online subjective examination, the students write answers in subjective and objective and describe the answer

assessment with the answers stored in the database model automatically to match keywords and get grades depending on the student's answer[23][24].

Fig (1): Subjective Examination System.

2. Components Of Question Answering System

A Question answering system contains three main parts: question classification (Question processing), information retrieval (Document processing), and answer extraction (Answer processing) [25]. The user writes a question using the user query interface. Then this query is used to extract all the possible answers for the input question. The architecture of the Question Answering system is as shown in Fig. (1)

Fig (2). Component of Question Answering system

3. Significance Subjective Examination

It is clear that most researchers worked in developing automated assessment systems for subjective questions in many languages. We can mention some points which a significance of the efficient automated assessment system for subjective questions should have the following features:

1. Most of capabilities for automated assessment system without need to human intervention.
2. Decreasing in computational complexity to provide a fast-automated assessment for subjective examination.
3. Efficient capability allows setting exam papers and quizzes in every semester.

4. Different Types of Questions based on Bloom's Taxonomy

Bloom's taxonomy is a multi-faceted model that promotes progressive learning with six levels of complexity. These six levels include **Remembering**, **Understanding**, **Applying**, **Analysing**, **Evaluating**, and **Creating**. Bloom's taxonomy encourages students to engage in knowledge at a deeper and more interactive level, to apply what they learn with a real-world perspective, rather than simply taking the information to the board. Questions a frequently used question expression experimental knowledge [26]. A classification system in Bloom's taxonomy is used to describe and classify different levels of human understanding. Teachers generally use Bloom's texts to inform or guide the development of exams (exams and other student learning assessments), curriculum (units, courses, projects, and other learning activities), and teaching methods such as questioning techniques [27]. According to the general agreement, QA Systems are categorized based on the following support purpose:

Open-domain QA: This type of QA handles questions almost anything, and may only depend on public ontologies and world knowledge. On the other hand, these programs often have more available information to them to issue a response. The system takes the NL query as input more than as a collection of words [28].

Closed-domain QA: This type of QA handles questions under certain conditions background (for example, Education or Bank), and is visible as an easy task because NLP programs can exploit particular domain information that is regularly organized into ontologies. Alternatively, a closed domain may refer to a situation where only a limited number of questions are allowed, as descriptive questions asking rather than process details [29].

Table (1): Bloom’s Taxonomy with Synonyms and Illustrative Verbs [30]

Objective	Definition	Synonyms	Illustrative verbs	level
Evaluation	encourage students to develop ideas and make value decisions about issues based on specific criteria	Estimate Assessment	Justify, conclude, Determinate, Evaluate, Judge, Measure, and verify.	High level dependent on student's reasoning ability.
Synthesis	Motivate students to do something new using a mix of ideas from different sources to create something new.	Combination, fusion, creation.	Edit, merge, create, generate, formulate, predict.	Hoq
Analysis	Encourage learners to break things down into parts, explain patterns and relationships between parts, separate information.	The study, Scrutiny, Breakdown.	Analyse, divide, define, distinguish, retrieve, research, classify, compare.	Hoq
Application	encourage learners to apply or transfer learning in their own lives or a different context from the subject	Use purpose appliance	Apply, compare, display, evaluate, link, solve, apply	Hoq
Comprehension	test students' ability to summarize and explain in their own words without having to deal with anything	Understanding Grasp	Divide, describe, explain, recognize, summarize, estimate, and derive.	Log
Knowledge	Test students’ ability to memorize and recall terms.	Information Facts Data	Memorize, define, identify, sketch, discuss, state, write, list, name.	Lowest level dependent on students memory ability

5. Question Answering System Approaches

5.1 Linguistic approach

A question answering system requires an understanding of natural language texts, languages , and general knowledge. Therefore, most of the previous researchers relied on artificial intelligence (AI) based methods that incorporate natural language resolution (NLP) techniques and knowledge base or corpus to build QA logics. The information data is organized in the form of production rules, lines, frames, templates (represented by triple relationships), ontologies, and ancient networks, which are used during the analysis of questionnaires. Language techniques such as marking, marking POS, and page use are used in the user's query to make it a straightforward query that removes the correct answer from a structured database. However, posting specific domain information sets a load limit as a different application domain requires different grammar and map rules. Also, building a proper knowledge base is a time-consuming process, so these programs are often used for problems with the long-term needs of a particular domain. BASEBALL by Green et al. [31] Answering a Question about the baseball game front is over details, closed domain. Clark et al [32] knowledge-based answer to questions with an understanding engine computer. Woods [33] compares and evaluates

chemical analysis data on rocky and sandy moons. Joseph Weizenbaum [34] attempts to mimic basic human interaction Questions and answers exchange. Bobrow et al. [35] the dialog system run on the framework of the Genial Understand system also uses a structured database as a source of information. CquarcHao et al [36] Rule-based Chinese QA system for Comprehension reading test. Mishra et al [37] Web databases for local information. Katz [38] STARTQA System The QA Web-based system can answer millions of English questions by places. Rilloff et al [39] Rule-base QA system for learning comprehension tests, all is a closed domain.

5.2 The statistical approach

Offers better results than other methods. Online text writing and mathematical methods are independent of the programming languages of the questions and form the questions in a kind of natural language. Mostly the entire QA statistical system uses the mathematical process in the QA system as a Support vector machine, Bayesian Classifiers, maximum entropy models [40] [41]. Suzuki et al [42] SVM answer selecting an open source QA domain response system. Moschitti [43] Question and answer in stages and tested used Support Vector Machine. Shortcut et al. [44] used N-gram data mining used mathematical chucker quizzes on chunks/phrases asked in a search engine. Ittycheriah et al [45] a great artificial model for the classification of questions based on various N-gram or word bags. Cai et al. [46] Similarity Sentence Model. Chinese QA Web-based system with response validation.

5.3 Pattern matching approach

Uses the expressive power of text patterns to replace the engagement process involved in other competition methods. Surface Pattern based [53] this method removes responses from the restructured text structure based on a wide range of patterns. The answer to the question is identified based on similarities between their display patterns with certain semantics. These patterns are similar to regular expressions. Although designing this use of patterns requires a lot of skill from time to time but the method has shown great accuracy. Saxena et al [54] a pattern corresponding to the semantic type and the semantic category are used with a difficult question. Greenwood et al [55] the property name appendix name is used to make the same text response pattern. Hovy et al. [56] higher reading text patterns for QA program that you have implemented the default self-study environment. Zhang et al [57] Low-level Web Mine and Comparison How to Answer Questions. Soubbtin et al [58] the response pattern as the correct response clues. Template Based Approach the template is a pre-programmed framework for questions with business Slots that should be strongly completed by the parameters. Uses a query designed to extract the answer from the database. Focus on making formatted responses in person, but default on the semantic web. Gunawardena et al [59] Pre-processing text to get the most appropriate template response Closed system for understanding SMS language. Unger et al [60] Resource Description Framework (RDF) QA-based project of the Template over RDF data SPARQL resource Description Framework (RDF) SPARQL RDF Questionnaire RDF, Sneiders [61] frequently asked Question (FAQ) Automatic QA using a question template that covers a thought imaginary data model.

Table (2): Comparison between types of approaches.

approaches	Types of Questions	Collections	Reliability
Linguistic approach	Factoid/Deep	Handmade test collections	Highly reliable as the answers are taken from the database.
Statistical approach	Non Factoid, Complex and Shallow factoids.	TREC,NTIRC,,C LEF, Test collections.	It is reliable as most of these programs used a controlled method.
Pattern approach	Factoid, Definition adjective, data of birth.	Handmade test collections	Depending on the source of the information.

Other systems based on hybrid process a Kwok et al MULDER [62] was fully self-contained, a common goal of QAS to generate feedback from the web with minimal user effort. The program was based on a combination of linguistic and mathematical approaches and is widely recall by 64.5. Xia et al [63] has combined the Rule-base classifier with the SVM classifier and have shown Precision and recall of 96.22%. Chakrabarti et al [64] follow the established language and structure patterns, it depends directly on the above patterns from the WordNet structure to determine the type of response. ASQA [65] and IBM's question answering in WATSON System [66] ASQA used more biography query patterns and interventions to address the meaning and related questions while WATSON competed with real-time human winners on the American TV quiz show Jeopardy and provides 70% specificity.

6. Overview Trce Questions Answering Tracks

In 1999 [67]. The methodology and description used in this study are mean reciprocal rank (Trec-8), the question answer limited between 50 or 250 bytes and twenty organizations are participating in the QA track. The dataset was a Collection of documents 1.5 gigabytes and 200 short answers, fact-based. Document collection newspaper article. The accuracy of the correct response is more than 2/3 of the questions. They used the English language.

2000 [68]. The answer is limited from 25 -50 bytes Question closed class and 28 participation in trec-9 (newspaper/test of a question) track. The dataset contained 500 questions additional 193, NIST ranking 1000 documents, and 50 documents per question. At last 36 groups submitted 92 runs to the question answering track they used the English language.

2001 [69]. QA track third running off track in Trec was used mean reciprocal rank (MRR), Foster research to retrieve answers more than documents in response to the question. The dataset was 25 questions as list task in the articles contain 979, 000, 3,033 megabytes of text distributed as 36 groups submitted a total of run on QA tack in the English language.

2002 [70]. The effort to get the benefits of large-scale evaluation, it's repeated from the 2001 list but major differences of systems in return exact answer. The dataset was QA track depends on one response for each 500 test questions. The collection is known as (AQUAINT) Corpus of English News Text.

2003 [71]. Pattern matching in (Web) using Web Ngram Mining and Collection Ngram Mining, Tequesta is a stream of a linguistically informed approach to QA, the dataset was text collection from web local AQAINI corpus. Corpus use top-ranking documents from Google. Matching documents using a Boolean query in the retrieval engine in the English language

2004 [72]. They used the automated regular expression, Present addition for KITKAT for 2004 QA system, named entities tags, and used a vector matching system and partial matching algorithm, the dataset was AQUAINT corpus of 150 characters and it is used a synonym system from WorldNet in the English language.

2005 [73]. Table module display to generate more candidate answers, upgrade a Tequesta stream encoding a document collection and Named entity recognizer, the dataset was 25 test topics, Document collection paragraphs for 400 characters in the English language,

2006[74].Complex, interactive question answering (CiQA), series of factoid, CiQA contain a framework for participants, TREC 2005 QA relationship task and the TREC 2005 HARD track, the dataset has contained a total of 403 factoid questions, 89 list questions, 75 Other questions, each series contains 6–9 questions used the English language.

2007 [75]. Answers in a series of related questions, evaluation methods discuss the QA task, the dataset was series of factoid, list, and “Other” questions 100 documents as retrieved by the PRISE system used English language.

2015 [76] used Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR), vibrational expectation maximization (EM) algorithm, Answer Candidate Generation via Entity Linking used Feature Generation and Ranking. Original dataset 1902 questions, 202 questions from TREC 12 and 1700 from TREC 8-11 for training used the English language.

2016 [77].Used in a popular community question answering Site Yahoo Answers (YA) to automatic of the question evaluate and measuring its ROUGE and METEOR-based similarity. It's manually provided by NIST assessors. The data set was used Yahoo Answers Questions and YA data a set of 1000 YA questions in English.

2017 [78]. Focused on a comparative study in Biomedical QA and Tec Genomics track. Datasets related to Biomedical Question Answering (BioQA) , ADLC corpus in English.

7. Conclusion

An online examination web service has been implemented based on the proposed mechanism. The proposed mechanisms are efficient in the performance and grading process for subjective questions. The Automated Exam Questions Used for Online Computer Examination will be beneficial to universities, schools, and colleges with the aim of learning by simplifying the skills and capabilities of the test cell. We have seen that the choice of a technique is very problematic. A hybrid approach and combining different methods provide fast results, increased higher results in the form of best accuracy and recall actions. However, it was realized that question answer methods based on linguistic, statistical, and pattern based approaches would receive serious attention, and received the attention of a large number of

question answer systems researchers. The effectiveness of QA systems increases by combining a range of processes to detect the inefficiency of each operation as seen in the integrated implementation, but these operations are either too expensive for a simple QA system or too expensive and time consuming for complex ones, hence the need for better ways to integrate strategies into QA systems. The issuance of a QA program is also based on a good knowledge base and a clear understanding of user queries. This understanding is extracted using NLP techniques. Failure on the part of these methods affects the responses generated by the system. Future research should focus on the use and application of existing strategies, which improve QA. This will encourage the re-use of quality modules and help researchers to focus and deal with differentiated research problems. The further study concludes that the effectiveness of technology is important for the smooth processing of online examination systems.

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